

Studies on Active Aluminium Halides Complexes of Organo Phosphorus Derivatives

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Abstract:

In the present work, the reactions of Aluminium chloride, phosphine derivatives in presence of alkyl/aryl chlorides have been carried out in organic solvents at room temperature. The electrical conductivity measurements of the complexes were carried out in their $10^{-3}M$ solution in nitromethane and DMSO solvent medium. The infrared spectra for and near of the products were recorded on IR-Spectro photometer. These studies confirmed the ionic nature of the products. The IR spectral data of the complexes have been discussed on the basis of cationic and anionic spectra.

Introduction:

The biological active Aluminium halides complexes containing phosphorus atom have been gaining importance now a days in various fields so much so that phosphorus chemistry has developed a separate class of Bio-chemistry. Martin¹ studied electrical properties of adducts of metal chloride like $AlCl_3$, $FeCl_3$, $SnCl_4$ and $SbCl_5$ with phosphorus pentachlorides in solvent like nitrobenzene and acetonitrile and found these complexes to be good conductor of electricity pure phosphorus pentachloride liquid is non conducting and trigonal bipyromidal arrangement of chlorine atoms round phosphorus has been confirmed by I.R. and Roman spectral studies²⁻⁵.

Experimental:

Estimation of Aluminium due to the presence of phosphorus in this complex, Aluminium is determined as ferric phosphate.⁶ A weight quantity of the compound was taken in to a beaker, containing distilled water. Acidified with 5-6ml of conc. HNO_3 and heated to dryness to convert phosphorus in to phosphate. The process was repeated 2-3 times to ensure complete oxidation. The residue, after removal of HNO_3 , was dissolved in distilled water. The solution was transferred to a 250ml volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with distilled water 50ml of this solution was used for estimation of Aluminium and phosphorus separately. 50ml of the above solution was diluted to 200ml in a beaker. Two drops of Methyl

orange indicator were added and the soln. was neutralized with ammonia Acetic acid was added dropwise to red colour. 10g of diammonium hydrogen phosphate was added and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.0 by boiling for 30 minutes and allowed to stand for two hours. Filtered and washed the precipitate with 2% hot ammonium nitrate solution. The filter paper and the precipitate were by gentle beating in a silica crucible. The carbon was burnt initially at low temperature and finally the residue was ignited at 600-650°C to a constant weight. The residue was weighted as FeSO₄. 50ml of the solution was boiled with HNO₃ after dilution to 150ml, 3-5 of citric acid was added in order to complex the Aluminium and the solution was boiled. After cooling a few crops of methyl red indicator were added. Freshly prepared magnesia mixture was slowly introduced. Concentrated Ammonia solution was then added slowly, with vigorous stirring, until colour of the solution changed to yellow. Stirring was continued for about 5 minutes without screeching the sides of the beaker. The solution was kept alkaline by adding ammonia solution and the solution was kept for about 6 hours. The ppt. thus obtained was weighted in a sintered glass crucible (G-4) as Mg(NH₄)PO₄ 6H₂O.

Reaction of Aluminium (III) Chloride

1. Reaction between Aluminium (III) Chloride, trichlorophosphine and t-butyl chloride: Analysis

Found Al, 14.38; P, 8.00; Cl, 62.89%

Required for [Bu^tPCl₃] [AlCl₄]

Al, 14.24; P, 7.91; Cl, 63.29%

2. Reaction between Aluminium (III) Chloride, trichlorophosphine and iso-butyl chloride : Analysis

Found Al, 14.47; P, 7.87; Cl, 63.01%

Required for [BuⁱPCl₃] [AlCl₄]

Al, 14.24; P, 7.91; Cl, 63.29%

3. Reaction between Aluminium (III) Chloride, trichlorophosphine and t-amyl chloride : Analysis

Found Al, 14.00; P, 7.75; Cl, 60.83%,

Required for [Am^tPCl₃] [AlCl₄]

Al, 13.75; P, 7.62; Cl, 61.11%

4. Reaction between Aluminium (III) Chloride, trichlorophosphine and cyclohexyl chloride : Analysis

Found Al, 13.28; P, 7.35; Cl, 59.05%

Required for [C₆H₁₁PCl₃] [AlCl₄]

Al, 13.35; P, 7.40; Cl, 59.35%

Table – I

Vibrational Assignments in Aluminium Complexes

a. [RPCl₃]⁺

S. No.	Compound	A ₁ ∓ P–C (R) cm ⁻¹	A ₁ ∓ P–C cm ⁻¹	A ₁ 6 PCl ₃ cm ⁻¹	E ₁ ∓ P–Cl cm ⁻¹	E ₁ 6 R–P–Cl cm ⁻¹
1.	[Bu ^t PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	785s	490m	228sh	630s	260w
2.	[Am ^t PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	790s	495m	230sh	635s	209w
3.	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	795s	485sh		638s	
4.	[(Ph ₃ C)PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	788s	508sh		635s	

b. [RPhPCl₃]⁺

Sr. No.	Compound	A' ∓ P–C(Ph) cm ⁻¹	A' ∓ P–C (R) cm ⁻¹	A' ∓ P–Cl (sym) cm ⁻¹	Overtone or combination cm ⁻¹	A'' ∓ P–Cl (sym) cm ⁻¹	A'' 6 R–P–Cl cm ⁻¹
1.	[Bu ^t PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	1440,1000vs	795s	498m	640s	605w	233w
2.	[Am ^t PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	1445,1000vs	785s	507w	630s	610w	230w
3.	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	1450,1005s	793s	505sh	645s	612m	227sh
4.	[(Ph ₃ C)PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	1450,998s	795s	508sh	640s	608m	

Table – II

Infrared Spectra of AlCl₄⁻

Sr. No.	Compound	∓ ₃ (Fe–Cl) cm ⁻¹
1.	[Bu ^t PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	385 vs
2.	[Am ^t PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	383 vs
3.	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	382 vs
4.	[(Ph ₃ C)PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	384 vs

Table – III

Mossbacer Spectra of Aluminium Compounds

Sr. No.	Compound	Quadrupole Splitting* O Eq mm/sec	Isomer shift* 6 mm/sec
1.	[Bu ^t PhPCl ₂] [AlCl ₄]	1.2	0.40
2.	[Bu ^t PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	2.0	0.49
3.	[Bu ^{iso} PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	0.65	0.39
4.	[Am ^t PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	1.9	0.40
5.	[C ₆ H ₁₁ PCl ₃] [AlCl ₄]	0.55	0.40

Results and Discussion:

The present of the Tetra Chloroaluminate (III) anion AlCl₄ was confirmed by U.V. spectral and mossbauer studies. Ultras violet and visible and infrared spectral studies of the complexes Si(acac)₃ AlCl₃, Ge(acac)₃ AlCl₄ and Ti(acac)₃ AlCl₄ by Bencraft et al⁷ had further confirmed the presence of tetrahedral AlCl₄⁻ anion. The infrared spectral study of the alkyl trichlorophonium (RPhPCl₄)⁺ cations in all complexes show a weak absorption between 785-790 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to P-C (alkyl) vibrations. Very strong absorption at 1000 cm⁻¹ and 1440cm⁻¹ are due to P-Ph vibration similar observations have been reported earlier at 998 cm⁻¹ and 1439 cm⁻¹ respectively⁸. The ultraviolet and visible spectra of the Tetrachloroaluminate (III) ion have been observed at 236, 308, 340 and 445 nm which is quite in arrangement with the result obtained at 240, 314, 362 and 447 nm respectively. This is also in agreement with the observed results for AlCl₄ in [Ti(acac)₃] [AlCl₄]⁸ at 385 cm⁻¹. In the solid state the magnetic susceptibility measurement studies of these Aluminium compounds are in the range of 5.34 to 5.828 B.M. suggestive of strongly paramagnetic nature. The mossbauer spectra of some of these compounds were taken on constant velocity can drive set up. The isomer shift and quadrupole splitting of some of the complexes have been given in the Table. The isomer shift(s) of compounds is in the range of 0.35 to 0.49 mm/sec at room temperature.

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